

Dear Members of the SeqCode community

The ballot to amend the SeqCode as was proposed by Whitman et al. 2023 (<https://doi.org/10.1038/s43705-023-00303-y>) has been completed and both proposals have been accepted and are adopted with immediate effect. The Legislative Commission will now update the SeqCode and the revised version, clearly labelled with an updated version number, will be posted on the SeqCode and Registry websites.

The detail of the two proposals and the outcome of the ballot are as follow:

Ballot on Proposal 1, to address problems related to conflicts between published *Candidatus* names and the SeqCode rules of priority:

Rule 23d [original rule]

The priority date of names of taxa of rank higher than genus proposed after 1 January 2022 is the same as the priority date of the corresponding type genus name. The priority date for names published before 1 January 2022 is the same as their priority under the ICNP.

Rule 23d [amended rule, new text underlined]

The priority date of names of taxa of rank higher than genus proposed after 1 January 2022 is the same as the priority date of the corresponding type genus name unless there is a published *Candidatus* name for the taxon. In that case, the date of publication of the *Candidatus* name establishes priority for the *Candidatus* name upon validation unless there is an ICNP name validly published for the same taxon before 1 January 2022, in which case the date of valid publication of the ICNP name establishes priority. Validating existing *Candidatus* higher taxa names requires validation of a type genus name with an appropriate stem and the associated names for the subordinated higher taxonomic ranks where appropriate. However, this protection of *Candidatus* names is lost if the *Candidatus* name is not validated by 1 January, 2027. The priority date for names published before 1 January 2022 is the same as their priority under the ICNP. This rule is retroactive to 1 January, 2022.

Note 1. After 1 January 2027, it is strongly recommended that genus names are proposed to preserve published *Candidatus* names for higher taxa, when appropriate, to allow validation of existing *Candidatus* names.

Accepted the proposed amendment to Rule 23d	55
Rejected the proposed amendment to Rule 23d	2
Abstained	7

Ballot on Proposal 2, to clarify procedures for correction of typographic and/or orthographic errors during registration of SeqCode names:

Rule 48 [original]

The original spelling of a name or epithet must be retained, except for typographic or orthographic errors.

An unintentional typographical or orthographic error later corrected by the author is to be accepted in its corrected form without affecting the status and date of valid publication. It can also be corrected by a subsequent author who may or may not mention that the spelling is corrected. However, the abbreviation “corrig.” (*corrigendum*) may be appended to the name if an author wishes to draw attention to the correction. Succeeding authors may be unaware that the original usage was incorrect and use the spelling of the original author(s). Other succeeding authors may follow the correction of a previous author or may independently correct the spelling themselves, but in no case is the use of corrig. regarded as obligatory. None of these corrections affects the status and date of validation.

Note. The liberty of correcting a name or epithet must be used with reserve, especially if the change affects the first syllable and above all the first letter of the name or epithet.

Rule 48 [amended rule, new text underlined]

The original spelling of a name or epithet must be retained, except for typographic or orthographic errors.

An unintentional typographical or orthographic error in an effectively published name may be corrected before or after validation in the Registry by the author or the SeqCode Registry curators. The name is to be accepted in its corrected form without affecting the status and date of valid publication. It can also be corrected by a subsequent author in a peer-reviewed publication. That publication may or may not mention that the spelling is corrected. In that case, the authors or SeqCode Registry curators must update the name in the SeqCode Registry. ~~However,~~ The abbreviation “corrig.” (*corrigendum*) may be appended to the name if an author wishes to draw attention to the correction. Succeeding authors may be unaware that the original usage was incorrect and use the spelling of the original author(s). Other succeeding authors may follow the correction of a previous author or may independently correct the spelling themselves, but in no case is the use of corrig. regarded as obligatory. None of these corrections affects the status and date of validation.

Note 1. The liberty of correcting a name or epithet must be used with reserve, especially if the change affects the first syllable and above all the first letter of the name or epithet.

Note 2. When feasible, as a courtesy, the SeqCode Registry curators will inform one or more authors of the effective publication that typographical or orthographic errors have been corrected in the Registry.

Accepted the proposed amendment to Rule 48	58
Rejected the proposed amendment to Rule 48	3
Abstained	3